

The Economics and Ethics of Abolishing Social Security

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Abstract

The fact that social security is a rip-off is becoming more generally known as the system approaches bankruptcy. Like any Ponzi scheme, those who got in early stood to gain. But the system has insurmountable problems. People are living longer due to advances in medicine, so they take money out of the system longer. The birth rate has declined, so there are not as many people paying into the system. As the baby boomers near retirement age, more people will be drawing from the system and fewer people will be paying into it. Proposed solutions put forth to avoid or postpone bankruptcy have included reducing benefits, increasing taxes, postponing the retirement age and means testing -- allowing only those who need it to be able to receive benefits. The author discusses the economic and ethical issues that would be involved in the debate to abolish Social Security.

The fact that social security is a rip-off is becoming more generally known as the system approaches bankruptcy.² Like any

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² The exact date when Social Security will go bankrupt is not known, of course. However, one recent estimate is 2029. The projected bankruptcy date gets closer each time an estimate is made. Outflows are expected to exceed inflows as early

Ponzi scheme, those who got in early stood to gain. But the system has insurmountable problems. People are living longer due to advances in medicine,³ so they take money out of the system longer. The birth rate has declined, so there are not as many people paying into the system. As the baby boomers near retirement age, more people will be drawing from the system and fewer people will be paying into it.⁴ Proposed solutions put forth to avoid or postpone bankruptcy have included reducing benefits, increasing taxes,⁵ postponing the retirement age and means testing -- allowing only those who need it to be able to receive benefits.

In theory there is a trust fund. As taxes are withheld from workers' paychecks and as employers are taxed, the money flows into a pool for a few months before it is distributed to current recipients. And a portion of the present surplus is borrowed against to finance the federal budget deficit, which weakens the system and makes it less solvent.⁶

Those who have paid into the fund have no inherent claim on any of the funds. Taxpayers who die before retirement are not entitled to any of the money they have poured into the system and neither are their heirs. If a similar investment scheme were made by a private insurance company, the corporate officers would be arrested for fraud. Yet the social security system has been a sacred

as 2012. See Michael Tanner, *The Other Trust Fund Report*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-tanner4.html>.

³ Carrie Lips, *Bad News for Social Security: There May Be a Cure for Cancer*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-21.html>.

⁴ In 1950 there were 16 workers for every Social Security recipient. Now there are only 3.3 and by 2030 there will be less than two. See Michael Tanner, *The Other Trust Fund Report*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-tanner4.html>.

⁵ Timothy J. Penny, *Please, Not Another Payroll Tax Hike*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-17.html>.

⁶ About 86.5% of the money collected is paid out in benefits. The remaining 13.5% is lent to the federal government to meet operating expenses. So there really is no trust fund. Michael Tanner, *Social Security Privatization and Economic Growth*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-tanner1.html>.

cow since it was founded in the 1930s. It is time to slaughter this sacred cow.

Some economists have advocated privatization as the way to save the system.⁷ Rather than paying into the government's phony trust fund, workers would pay into a private investment trust that they would actually be able to claim as property when they retire. Since it is their property, their heirs would be able to inherit. The massive pool of funds that would accumulate would be available for investment, thus leading to a business and stock market boom. Interest rates would drop, making it easier to finance a home. Those who placed money into the system for a number of years would be able to retire millionaires.⁸ According to Martin Feldstein of Harvard University, "the combination of the improved labor market incentives and the higher real return on savings has a net present value gain of more than \$15 trillion, an amount equivalent to 3 percent of each future year's GDP forever."⁹ Any number of good things would happen.

The big question is how do we get from here (the present system) to there (a private system)? What would happen to those now (or soon to be) on the system if the system went private.¹⁰

⁷ Michael Tanner, *Social Security Privatization and Economic Growth*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-tanner1.html>; Edward H. Crane, *The Case for Privatizing America's Social Security System*, address to S.O.S. Retraite Sante, Paris, France, December 10, 1997, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-22.html>.

⁸ According to one estimate, a worker who is 25 stands to get between three and six times greater benefits under a private system than under Social Security. Michael Tanner, *The Other Trust Fund Report*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-tanner4.html>.

⁹ Michael Tanner, *Social Security Privatization and Economic Growth*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-tanner1.html>.

¹⁰ Chile was the first country to privatize its Social Security system, in 1981. Pension benefits in the private system are now 50 to 100 percent higher, adjusted for inflation, than they were in the state-run system. Chile's growth rate jumped from its historic 3 percent annual rate to a rate that has averaged 7 percent over the last 12 years. The savings rate jumped to 25 percent of GDP and the unemployment rate dropped to around 5 percent. See José Piñera, *In*

Various proposals have been put forth. For example, young people could elect to set aside a portion of their present social security payments in a private fund, and the remainder of their social security taxes could continue to be used by those presently (or soon to be) drawing benefits. That way, those presently (or soon to be) drawing benefits would continue to do so.¹¹

The problem with this solution is that young workers would still be forced to pay for other peoples' benefits. Thus, it is unfair to young workers who have to pay into a system that they cannot draw from. Another solution that has been proposed is to sell federal land and use the proceeds to fully fund the present system. The federal government owns more than fifty percent of some western states, and owns substantial assets in every state. If these assets were sold, some estimates conclude that there would be enough money to fully fund the system for those who are presently on the system and for those who will retire within a few years.

These proposed solutions all have flaws. For one thing, they all rely on coercion. Under the present system, those who work are forced to pay the pensions of those who don't work. If the system were privatized, those who work would be forced to set aside some amount determined by government to provide for their own retirement. Thus, one fatal flaw in any government regulated

Chile, They Went Private 16 Years Ago, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-19.html>. Argentina, Peru, Colombia, Bolivia, Mexico and El Salvador have also privatized their Social Security systems. Peter Ferrara, *Destiny of Freedom for Social Security?* <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-11.html>.

¹¹ One rather scary solution that has been proposed would be for the federal government to invest the funds in the capital markets. If this were done, the federal government would become the largest shareholder in most American businesses, and would be able to influence corporate policy. In all likelihood, corporate decisions would start to be made for political rather than economic reasons. Perhaps there would be restrictions on the types of company that the funds could be invested in. Such a possibility is not far-fetched, judging from what has taken place in the state public employee pension funds. See Michael Tanner, *Tom Daschle's Very Bad Idea*, <http://www.socialsecurity.org/articles/art-tanner3.html>.

pension scheme is that it is based on coercion rather than voluntary exchange.

The popular rebuttal to this line of reasoning goes something like this: If the government didn't force people to pay into some social security system, some of them wouldn't do it, and they would become wards of the state. But just because some people decide to spend their money currently rather than provide for their retirement, it does not follow that the rest of us must be forced to support them. The whole argument is based on a non sequitur. If some people do not exercise individual responsibility, it does not follow that those who are responsible should be forced to help them out. There may be some moral duty to help such people, but that choice should be left to individuals and charities. Morality exists only where there is choice, so it cannot be said that government has a moral duty to help these people, because in order to do so, government must resort to force (taxation), which negates morality.

The present social security system is based on the immoral principle of redistribution. Those who work are forced to transfer a portion of their earnings to those who do not work. The only way to end this immoral practice is to abolish social security. Those who advocate gradualism would argue: "What would happen to those presently on the system if we abolished social security today"? But this is not a legitimate question, just as the gradualists of the 1840s and 1850s argued that slavery must be abolished gradually so that the slaves would not be unemployed and so that the plantation owners would not go bankrupt. Such gradualist arguments are themselves bankrupt. If something is unjust, the only solution is to end the practice immediately, regardless of consequences. An injustice cannot continue to be perpetrated just because there may be some short-term losers.

In order to continue the system, it would be necessary for present workers to continue to pay a portion of their wages to people who are not working, which is inherently unfair to those who are forced to pay. The argument has been made that those now on social security are entitled to receive benefits because they

paid into the system for many years. But this line of reasoning involves another non sequitur. In effect, they are saying: "I was forced to contribute to other peoples' retirement, therefore the younger generation should be forced to contribute to my retirement." The money the older generation paid into the system has long since been spent. It has been stolen, in effect (since theft is defined as the taking of property without the owner's consent, and many people would not pay social security taxes if they had a choice). But it does not follow that a portion of the younger generation's income should be stolen to pay for someone else's benefits. "They stole from me, therefore I have a right to steal from you" is a morally bankrupt statement (as well as a non sequitur).

The only way to stop this injustice of social security is to abolish the system immediately, regardless of consequences. The sale of government assets plus private charity might or might not provide sufficient funds to take care of those who are presently (or soon to be) on social security, but that is beside the point. The only moral solution is immediate abolition, regardless of consequences.